

Validation of Vertical Wind Shear Methods

Session 2 Wind Europe Resource Assessment Workshop

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Content

- ✓ Data sets available
- ✓ Methods used: Shear methods and metrics
- ✓ Results
- ✓ Conclusions

Data set: 212 masts globally

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What type of information is available?

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Vertical extrapolation methods investigated

Wind Shear methods

Applied to

Resolution

Power Law

Power law :

$$V(z) = V(z_{ref}) \times \left(\frac{z}{z_{ref}}\right)^\alpha$$

Timeseries methods

10 mins

Frequency Distributions methods

Directional (12, 16, etc)

Log Law

Logarithmic law :

$$V(z) = V(z_{ref}) \times \frac{\ln(z/z_0)}{\ln(z_{ref}/z_0)}$$

Monthly/Hourly (12x24)

Timeseries method

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Timeseries method

Sheared up series

VS

Measured series

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Frequency distribution

Measured

Sheared up

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Error metrics

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Results

MAE

StdDev

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Results

MWS_Freqdist

Energy Freqdist

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Results

ShapeFreqdist

MWS_Freqdist

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Conclusions

- ✓ Timeseries methods show lowest errors in all metrics
- ✓ Timeseries methods are also better for recreating timeseries of wind speeds at other heights
- ✓ Power law shows lower error than log law on average. Some specific sites have shown better results, but no physical explanation could be used to explain it

Thanks for your attention. Questions?

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